

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Authoring the Blood Vasculature Geometry Table

Procedures for describing the geometric properties of blood vessels, such as length and diameter, in the blood vasculature geometry table

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Introduction

The procedures outlined in this document describe how to create and extend the [blood vasculature geometry table](#). This is an essential part of the Human Reference Atlas's goal to build a Vasculature Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF), which uses blood and lymph vascular pathways to describe the location of cells throughout the body.

Knowing the geometric properties of blood vessels, such as length, luminal diameter, and outer diameter helps identify vessels in specimens and align those specimens with the VCCF. The geometric properties are also useful for investigators in modeling the cardiovascular system and simulating blood flow through vessels. The primary audiences for this SOP are the authors and reviewers of the blood vasculature geometry table.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Data Provider** provides evidence-based data about blood vessel geometric properties to the Table Author.

The **Reviewer** is a domain expert in blood vasculature who reviews the diagrams and suggests corrections.

The **Table Author** is responsible for managing the content of the blood vasculature geometry table.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Data Provider	Lu Chen	lu.chen.3@stonybrook.edu

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Reviewer	TBD	
Table Author	Katherine Gustilo Griffin Weber	katherine.gustilo@cuanschutz.edu weber@hms.harvard.edu

Procedures

Obtaining Data for the Table

There are two ways to obtain vessel geometric properties for this table:

- The Table Author finds geometric properties of vessels that have been reported in the literature. An example is a journal article describing the results of a cadaveric study where blood vessel properties were physically measured.
- The Data Provider provides new experimental data (e.g., single-cell tissue analysis) about blood vessel geometric properties to the Table Author. An example is an unpublished dataset generated by computationally measuring the diameter of blood vessels from radiographic images.

The following information about vessel geometric properties should be collected:

- The vessel whose geometric property is being described. This vessel should correspond to one listed in the [Blood Vasculature ASCT+B Table](#).
- Determine the geometric property. Each row in the table should list a single property. The most common types are length (20 vessels), luminal diameter (71 vessels), and outer diameter (7 vessels). Other properties such as branching angle and branching depth may be added in future updates.
- If the geometric property is based on more than one specimen, the mean, standard deviation, and range should be collected if possible.
- The units used to measure the geometric property should be recorded.
- If possible, collect separate geometric property values by sex and population (e.g., race, ethnicity, geographic region) as reported in the publication or data source.
- The source (e.g., data DOI and a data portal or a reference to the publication where the geometric properties are listed) and the method used to measure the geometric property (e.g., Cadaveric study, Computed tomography, Ultrasound, Not specified) should be recorded.
- The same geometric property for a vessel can be listed multiple times on different rows in the table, corresponding to different sexes, populations, sources and methods. Note that the value of the geometric property might vary greatly between rows.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Table Metadata: First 10 Rows

Similar to other Human Reference Atlas (HRA) tables, the first 10 rows of the blood vasculature geometry table are reserved for metadata. Row 1 contains the name of this table “Blood Vasculature Geometry.” Row 2 is intentionally left blank. Rows 3-10 include information about the authors, reviewers, general reference publications, the DOI of the table, and the date and version of the table. For details about rows 3-10, see the SOP on [Authoring ASCT+B Tables](#).

Table Columns

See below for a list of columns and descriptions for listing the vessel geometric properties.

Table 2. Column descriptions for Blood Vasculature Geometry Tables.

Column	Description
Vessel	The name of the blood vessel.
Property	The characteristic of the vessel being described in this row of the table. For example, “length”, “luminal diameter”, and “outer diameter”.
Sex	The sex of the population corresponding to this row in the table. Possible values are “Female”, “Male”, “Both”, and “Unknown”.
Value	The value reported for the vessel property, typically representing a mean unless noted otherwise. For example, if the property is “length”, then this is the mean length of the vessel reported in the reference. If a range, rather than a mean or median is reported, then the value is “-1”.
StandardDeviation	The standard deviation of the vessel property. If none is reported in the reference, then “-1”.
RangeLow	The lower end of the range of the vessel property. If none is reported in the reference, then “-1”.
RangeHigh	The upper end of the range of the vessel property. If none is reported in the reference, then “-1”.
Units	The unit of measurement for the value, standard deviation, and range.
Population	The population of people used in the reference. For example, “American Study”, “Chinese Study”, or “Unknown”.
SampleSize	The number of vessels measured. If unknown, then “-1”.
Method	The technique used to measure the vessel. For example: “Cadaveric study”, “Computed tomography”, “Ultrasound”, or “Not specified”.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

ReferenceURL	If applicable, the url of the reference reporting the vessel property's value or range.
Reference	The reference (source) reporting the vessel property's value or range.
ReferenceDOI	If applicable, the DOI of the reference reporting the vessel property's value or range.
Notes	Additional information from the reference about the population or how the vessel property value or range was determined.

Review process

- Confirm that the format of the table follows the SOP.
- Identify rows in the table where the geometric property values do not seem plausible.
- Notify the Table Authors of any potential problems found so they can confirm that the source data were correctly copied to the table.

References and Resources

Boppana A, Lee S, Malhotra R, Halushka M, Gustilo KS, Quardokus EM, Herr BW 2nd, Börner K, Weber GM. Anatomical structures, cell types, and biomarkers of the healthy human blood vasculature. *Sci Data*. 2023 Jul 19;10(1):452. doi: 10.1038/s41597-023-02018-0. PMID: 37468503; PMCID: PMC10356915.

Börner K, Teichmann SA, Quardokus EM, Gee JC, Browne K, Osumi-Sutherland D, Herr BW 2nd, Bueckle A, Paul H, Haniffa M, Jardine L, Bernard A, Ding SL, Miller JA, Lin S, Halushka MK, Boppana A, Longacre TA, Hickey J, Lin Y, Valerius MT, He Y, Pryhuber G, Sun X, Jorgensen M, Radtke AJ, Wasserfall C, Ginty F, Ho J, Sunshine J, Beuschel RT, Brusko M, Lee S, Malhotra R, Jain S, Weber G. Anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas. *Nat Cell Biol*. 2021 Nov;23(11):1117-1128. doi: 10.1038/s41556-021-00788-6. Epub 2021 Nov 8. PMID: 34750582; PMCID: PMC10079270.

Weber GM, Ju Y, Börner K. Considerations for Using the Vasculature as a Coordinate System to Map All the Cells in the Human Body. *Front Cardiovasc Med*. 2020 Mar 13;7:29. doi: 10.3389/fcvm.2020.00029. PMID: 32232057; PMCID: PMC7082726.

Glossary

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

Blood Vasculature Geometry Table: A table that lists geometric properties, such as length and diameter, of selected blood vessels.

Geometric property: A physical characteristic of a blood vessel, such as length, luminal diameter, and outer diameter. It may be recorded as a single value if measured from an individual vessel or as a mean, standard deviation, or range if measured across multiple specimens.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The HRA is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The HRA provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

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